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Analyzing the Relationship between Career Management Practices and Job Satisfaction among College Workers in Ekiti State

Author's Details:

⁽¹⁾**AWOKOYA Oluwabunmi Adenike**

Department of Business Administration, Faculty of Management Sciences, Ekiti State University, Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

⁽²⁾**AGBETUYI, Helen Opeyemi**

Department of Business Administration, Faculty of Management Sciences, Federal University, Oye-Ekiti, Ekiti State, Nigeria

⁽³⁾**BANKOLE Oluwole Adeniyi**

Department of Business Administration, Faculty of Management Sciences, Ekiti State University, Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Abstract:

This study is to analyse the relationship between career management and job satisfaction among college workers in Ekiti State. A descriptive survey research design was adopted through the questionnaire. Staff of College of Health Science and Technology, Ijero Ekiti constituted the study population. The sample size was 148 which were selected using Yamane sampling formular. Primary data used for the study were gathered through structured questionnaire. Data gathered were analyzed using the Pearson product-moment correlation and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). The result showed that there is positive and significant relationship between career management job satisfactions. Thus, the study concluded that career management is positively and significantly related to job satisfaction with special reference to College workers in Ekiti State

Keyword: *Career, Career Management, Employee, Satisfaction*

INTRODUCTION

Employees are widely seen as vital resources for organisations, given their active contributions to the achievement of organisational objectives, a factor that should not be disregarded. In order to promote job satisfaction, it becomes necessary to equip employees with their distinct talents through efficient career management (Aseka, 2002). The desire or goal of all employees within an organisation is to achieve their full potential, which serves as a significant source of inspiration and motivation for their job satisfaction and dedication. According to Jusuf, Mahfudnurnajamuddin, Mallongi, and Latief (2016), there exists a favourable correlation between the level of career development opportunities provided to employees and their overall happiness and commitment levels. Employees are more likely to exhibit strong work performance and have elevated levels of job satisfaction when they are assigned to roles that align with their individual interests and competencies.

According to Siagian (2002), it is essential to assign employees to positions that align with their interests and talents while also considering their contributions towards fulfilling the organisation's human resource requirements. In the context of strategic human capital development, the career programme is widely recognised as a significant tool for employee development. It encompasses not only the job responsibilities of employees but also their attitudes, behaviours, and overall work-related circumstances (Greenhaus, Callanan, & Godshalk, 2000; Ismail, Daud, & Madrah, 2011; Puah & Ananthram, 2006). From this

standpoint, employers frequently develop and implement career programmes with the aim of facilitating workers' alignment of their interests and talents with organisational prospects, as well as their smooth adaptation to both present and future organisational transformations. The implementation of well-designed career programmes has the potential to effectively facilitate the advancement of individuals' careers inside organisations (Baruch, 2004; Martin, Romero, Valle, & Dolan, 2001). Hence, the current investigation aims to draw the interest of administrators and policymakers in public tertiary institutions towards the significance of mitigating job discontent, poor commitment, and turnover among college employees, specifically focusing on Ekiti State.

The issue of job satisfaction and dedication among public sector employees has emerged as a significant area of concern within the Nigerian education sector and other sectors. Employees at tertiary institutions often encounter challenges such as delayed staff promotions, promotions without corresponding salary increases, incomplete implementation of the new minimum wage, and unfavourable political practices that affect career progression and the appointments of key personnel. It is well acknowledged that a significant proportion of individuals in Nigeria engage in employment within institutions, primarily driven by financial remuneration. The individuals consistently fulfil their financial obligations, although they experience a lack of job satisfaction across all aspects. Individuals actively pursue other options, although their progress is impeded by suboptimal career management strategies. As a result, this phenomenon has contributed to an increase in the frequency at which faculty members of higher institutions engage in moonlighting activities, hence raising concerns about their efficacy and efficiency in fulfilling their core work responsibilities. Previous studies have mostly focused on career development and career planning within the Nigerian tertiary education system. However, there is a lack of emphasis on the effectiveness of career management, which is predominantly overseen by institutional management. Hence, the primary focus of this study would be to examine the correlation between career management and job satisfaction among college employees in Ekiti State.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Career management is frequently acknowledged as a derivative of contemporary career development. After individuals have formulated their professional objectives, they must possess the necessary skills, abilities, and values in order to effectively implement their career goals through the application of proper career management strategies. Subsequently, following the process of career planning, the subsequent phase entails the implementation of devised plans via suitable career management strategies. Hence, career management may be described as a continuous endeavour including the preparation, development, execution, and evaluation of career plans and strategies by individuals or in accordance with an organisation's career framework (Hall & Associates, 1986). Career management is an ongoing and perpetual endeavour that encompasses several aspects of an individual's professional journey. In light of this, career management can be described as the systematic procedure through which individuals gather information pertaining to their values, interests, skill strengths, and weaknesses, establish a career objective, and employ career strategies aimed at enhancing the likelihood of attaining said career goals (Greenhaus, Callanan, & Godshalk, 2000). In a similar vein, it is noteworthy that a gratifying professional trajectory may engender a sense of personal contentment, whereas inadequate career management or ill-advised choices in this domain can profoundly undermine an individual's overall state of psychological well-being (Greenhaus, Callanan, & Godshalk, 2000). Furthermore, the dynamic nature of the environment, characterised by shifts in company strategy, organisational restructuring, mergers and acquisitions, and technological advancements, necessitates the continuous management of one's career. Consequently, individuals are compelled to reassess their career options and make adjustments to their career trajectories. According to the findings of Greenhaus, Callanan, and Godshalk (2000), it is argued that good career management enables employees to make well-informed decisions that align with their abilities, ambitions, and personal principles, thereby enhancing organisational success (Adekola, 2011).

According to Dessler (2013), career management may be defined as the systematic approach that facilitates employees in gaining a deeper understanding of their professional talents and interests and subsequently using these skills and interests in a more efficient manner. According to Armstrong (2006), career management encompasses the provision of chances for individuals to advance and enhance their careers

while also ensuring that the organisation maintains a steady supply of talented individuals. According to Okwiet (2014), the rationale for career management is predominantly centred around the individual employee and their pursuit of personal goals rather than solely focusing on the organisational objectives (Dialoke, Nnaemeka, & Ojeka, 2016). According to Lyria, Namusonge, and Karanja (2017), career management may be evaluated based on the presence of organisational policies pertaining to employee development and advancement. Career management plays a crucial role in establishing career routes across all units of an organisation. It encompasses several elements, such as succession planning, career mentors, career centres, counselling facilities, and retirement preparation programmes. Additionally, it involves the implementation of procedures to guarantee effective performance management and feedback processes inside the organisation.

Job satisfaction or unhappiness is influenced by several factors, including an individual's work experience, educational attainment, skills, personal competency, and level of identification with the task at hand. The determination of an emotional reaction is contingent upon an individual's articulation of their personal sentiments (Adigun, Oyekunle, & Onifade, 2017). Amburgey (2005) argues that job satisfaction plays a crucial role in the overall performance of an organisation. According to Brown (2013), job satisfaction pertains to the subjective perceptions, cognitive evaluations, and behavioural inclinations of individuals within an organisational setting, which serve as indicators for anticipating employee conduct. Hence, job satisfaction may be employed as a component in assessments that contribute to the formulation of strategies for enhancing organisational performance. The long-term success of an organisation is contingent upon the happiness and motivation of its personnel. Existing literature suggests a clear correlation between job satisfaction and employee motivation (Hee, Ong, Ping, Kowang, & Fei, 2019). According to Bakotic (2016), employees exhibit job satisfaction and are anticipated to get enjoyment from their work experiences, resulting in reduced levels of stress. Moreover, contented personnel typically have a favourable perspective on their surroundings. According to Khalaf, Hmoud, and Obeidat (2019), the presence of a positive viewpoint inside an organisation or firm has a significant role in enhancing the performance of both personnel and the organisation as a whole.

A prosperous organisation often regards its employees as a primary factor or factors of enhanced quality and increased production. According to Gupta, Kaur, Gupta, Jain, and Sharma (2012), these organisations place a higher emphasis on workers as the primary drivers of progress than capital investment. Job satisfaction is widely recognised as a crucial determinant of the efficiency and effectiveness of commercial organisations. In contemporary times, there has been a notable shift in the priorities of organisations and service delivery management towards the well-being of their employees. This shift entails a heightened emphasis on comprehending the wants, requirements, personal objectives, and aspirations of employees. A contented employee is one who has a sense of satisfaction, leading to their overall performance in their role. The significance of job satisfaction becomes more evident when considering the numerous adverse outcomes associated with job discontent, such as reduced loyalty, heightened absenteeism, and an increased occurrence of accidents (Aziri, 2011).

Theoretical Framework

This study will be based on the theoretical framework of expectation theory. The notion of expectancy was formulated by Victor Vroom in 1964. According to the idea, motivation is influenced by an individual's anticipation of achieving a desired end and the level of appeal that objective holds for the individual. Individuals engage in a cognitive process wherein they assess the potential benefits they anticipate acquiring from a certain circumstance, evaluate the level of work they will be required to exert, and determine the perceived value of the outcome in relation to their own objectives. Nevertheless, the aspiration of each individual is to maximise their potential inside the workplace by advancing via the professional ladder or achieving career development through time. Given this perspective, the significance of expectation theory in examining the relationship between career management and work satisfaction becomes evident.

METHODOLOGY

Area of Study: The study was carried out in Ekiti State.

Research Design: This study employed a descriptive survey in the sense that it assisted the researcher gather first-hand information from the respondents. Since the study employed descriptive survey, primary source through structured questionnaire was used to gather information from the target respondents.

Population of the Study: Both academic staff and non-academic staff of College of Health Science and Technology, Ijoro Ekiti constituted the target population. Therefore, the population of this study is two hundred and thirty four (234) as revealed by the human resources management record of the college.

Sample and Sampling Techniques: The study respondents were conveniently sampled through Yamane (1967) sampling model. Therefore, one Hundred and forty eight (148) respondents is sampled. The formula is stated below:

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

n = anticipated sample size; N = population size; e = sampling error (0.05). Therefore the total sample size was computed as:

$$n = \frac{234}{1+234(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{234}{1.585}$$

$$n = 148.$$

Model Estimation Technique: The descriptive statistics to be used include percentage and frequency counts while the inferential statistics that would be used is Pearson Product Moment Correlation model for the objectives. The Pearson Product Moment Correlation formula is given as:

$$r_{xy} = \frac{n\sum x_i y_i - \sum x_i \sum y_i}{\sqrt{n\sum x_i^2}}$$

$$\sqrt{n\sum y_i^2}$$

Where r_{xy} = correlation coefficient showing the linear relationship between dependent and independent variables

X = Independent Variable (Career Management)

Y = Dependent Variable (Job Satisfaction)

DATA ANALYSIS AND PRESENTATION

This section presents the analysis of data, the data interpretation and discussion of the findings with regards to the objective of the study. The analysis of the respondent's demographic information is presented in table 1.

Table 1: Respondents Demographic Distribution

Variables	Frequency	Percent
Gender		
Male	63	42.6
Female	85	57.4
Total	148	100.0
Marital Status		
Single	36	24.3
Married	112	75.7
Total	148	100.0
Educational Qualification		
B.Sc	46	31.1
MBA/M.Sc	84	56.7
Ph.D	18	12.2

Total	148	100.0
Working Experience		
Below 5	24	16.2
6-10	61	41.3
11-15	36	24.3
16 Above	27	18.2
Total	148	100.0

Source: Field Survey, (2022)

Table 1 indicated that the male distribution was 63 (42.6%), while the female were 85 (57.4%). This implied that we have more female academic staff than male in the surveyed tertiary institutions in Ekiti State. Considering the marital status, 36 (24.3%) of the total respondents were single while 112 (75.7%) were married. The summary of response gathered here implied that larger populations of respondents are married.

It was also shown that 46 (31.1%) of the respondents were B.Sc holders, 84 (56.7%) respondents were MBA/M.Sc holders while 18 (12.2%) were Ph.D holders, which indicated that majority of the respondents were MBA/M.Sc holders. Responses also showed that 24 (16.2%) of the respondents have below 5 years work experience, 61 (41.3%) of the respondents have between 6-10 years of experience, 36 (24.3%) of the respondents have between 11-15 years of experience while 27 (18.2%) of the respondents have above 16 years of experience. This implied that a larger percentage of surveyed staff have between 6-10 years of experience.

Relationship between Career Management and Job Satisfaction

Relationship between career management and job satisfaction was subjected to Pearson product moment correlation and tested the hypothesis using analysis of variance (ANOVA) through F-Statistic.

Table 2: Relationship between Career Management and Job Satisfaction

Variables	Correlation Value	Sig (2-tailed)
Career Management	.565	.000
F-cal	125.577	
F-tab	3.89	

Source: Author's Field Survey, (2023)

Career Management and Job Satisfaction

Table 2 depicts the relationship that exists between career management and customer retention. The correlation coefficient value of career management (0.565) showed that there is a strong positive relationship between career management and customer retention thus implied that there is significant relationship between career management and customer retention among college workers in Ekiti State. This relationship has been found to be significant at 0.000 $p < 0.05$ for career management as the p-value which is shown in the sig (2-tailed) row as revealed on the Table.

Test of Hypothesis

The analysis of variance through F-test is used to test the overall significance of the model by comparing the F calculated with the F tabulated. It could be noted that the calculated value (125.577) of F distribution gave a value greater than the F tabulated (3.89). Hence, we accept H_1 and reject H_0 . The study rejected null hypothesis and accepted otherwise i.e. there is significant relationship between career management and job satisfaction among College workers in Ekiti State.

Discussion of Findings

Based on the findings of the research, it can be inferred that a significant portion of the survey respondents are female and married. Furthermore, in terms of educational attainment, respondents with a master's degree constitute a substantial proportion. Additionally, the majority of respondents have 6–10 years of professional

job experience. Nevertheless, the research revealed a noteworthy and statistically significant correlation between career management and work satisfaction inside the institution under investigation in Ekiti State, with a significance level of 0.05. Furthermore, the analysis of the F-statistic indicated that the alternate hypothesis was supported, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. This suggests a substantial association between career management and work satisfaction. The results are consistent with the study conducted by Lyria, Namusonge, and Karanja (2017), which examined the impact of career management on the organisational performance of companies listed on the Nairobi Securities Exchange. The findings indicate a significant and favourable correlation between career management and organisational success across the listed organisations.

Conclusion

The issue of career management holds significant importance inside Nigerian educational institutions since it plays a crucial role in the promotion of work satisfaction. Therefore, the extent to which career management is accepted or prioritised determines this outcome. According to the findings of the study, a significant positive correlation was observed between career management and job satisfaction among college workers in Ekiti State. The present study employed analysis of variance (ANOVA) to examine the research hypothesis, revealing a statistically significant association between career management and job satisfaction among college workers in Ekiti State. Consequently, the study supports the alternative hypothesis and rejects the null hypothesis, leading to the conclusion that there exists a positive and statistically significant correlation between career management and job satisfaction among college workers in Ekiti State.

Recommendations

Based on the aforementioned findings, the study suggests that it is important to ensure fairness and transparency in the criteria and procedures pertaining to promotions. The implementation of objectivity in career management systems, namely via performance evaluation, is crucial for organisations to effectively identify suitable workers for training, development, and increased responsibilities. This process aims to adequately prepare individuals for higher roles within the firm. The efficacy of career management practices can serve as a deterrent against unethical political conduct among college personnel and contribute to the enhancement of work satisfaction within the Nigerian education sector.

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